

PHILOLOGY

ХУДОЖНІЙ СВІТ Г. СКОВОРОДИ З ДОМІНАНТОЮ «ДУША»

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H. SKOVORODA'S ARTISTIC WORLD WITH THE DOMINANT «SOUL»

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Анотація

У статті аналізується домінанта «душа» в поетичному просторі Г. Сковороди, встановлено її роль у розкритті художнього сенсу твору. Особливу увагу присвячено дослідженню міфології безсмертя душі і тіла, інтерпретації, популярного в давній українській літературі, мотиву «саду» і «розп'яття» та одного із найдавніших сакральних знаків – «хреста».

З'ясовано, що поет креативно використав та інтерпретував біблійні образи, біблійне цитування й культову атрибутику, що представили нові алюзії, співвіднесені з суспільно-культурним життям в Україні XVIII ст., підтвердили універсальність його лірики. У ставленні до природи поетика його лірики репрезентувала тотожності між «душею» і «природою».

Простежено риси світобачення митця, базовані на всебічному переосмисленні усталеного тематичного кола і світоглядних домінант, як от: пошуки щастя, зумовлені потребою встановлення рівноваги між власним внутрішнім світом і мінливою дійсністю; подвійний характер людської природи й всесвіту; мотив смерті у безперервній єдності з життям. Констатуємо, що в художній спадщині Г. Сковороди продемонстровано два рівні сприймання світу: одна площина – це розчарування від світу, друга – зумовлена спонтанною вірою у цінність людської душі.

Установлено, що Г. Сковорода переконливо доводив: людина повинна досягнути Божественну мудрість, зрозуміти Біблію шляхом символічного її сприйняття, адже все пізнається лише в Богові й через Бога. З цією метою він окреслив духовні орієнтири, що допомагають втілити бажаний ідеал. Використання сутнісних образів-символів працюють на основне естетичне завдання його поезії – усвідомлення людиною сенсу її життя, її становлення, розвитку, призначення й місця в суспільстві і всесвіті. Душа ліричного суб'єкта поезії Г. Сковороди є першою сходинкою, з якої починається пізнання універсуму.

Abstract

The article analyzes the dominant "soul" in the poetic space of G. Skovoroda, and establishes its role in revealing the artistic meaning of the work. The study of the mythology of the immortality of soul and body paid particular attention, the interpretation popular in ancient Ukrainian literature, the motif of "garden" and "crucifixion" and one of the oldest sacred signs - "cross".

The poet creatively used and interpreted biblical images, biblical quotations and paraphernalia cult, which presented new allusions related to the socio-cultural life in Ukraine in the XVIII century, confirmed the universality of his lyrics. The poetics of his lyrics represented the identity between "soul" and "nature", in relation to nature.

The features of the artist's worldview are traced, based on a comprehensive rethinking of the established thematic circle and worldview dominants, such as: the search for happiness, due to the need to establish a balance between his own inner world and changing reality; the dual nature of human nature and the universe; the motive of death in continuous unity with life. We state that G. Skovoroda's artistic heritage demonstrates two levels of perception of the world: one plane is disappointment with the world; the other is due to spontaneous belief in the value of the human soul.

A person should comprehend the Divine wisdom; understand the Bible through its symbolic perception, because only in God and through God everything known, which G. Skovoroda convincingly proved. To this end, he outlined the spiritual guidelines that help to realize the desired ideal. The use of essential images-symbols work on the main aesthetic task of his poetry - a person's awareness of the meaning of his life, its formation, development, purpose and place in society and the universe. The soul of the lyrical subject of G. Skovoroda's poetry is the first step from which the knowledge of the universe begins.

Ключові слова: образ, символ, домінанта «душа», мотив «саду», Біблія, Бог.

Keywords: image, symbol, dominant “soul”, motif of “garden”, Bible, God.

H. Skovoroda's artistic world with the dominant “soul”

The symbol “heart” in the Bible, where “it (heart) means a soul and a spirit, the path to the highest truth” [8, p. 709], is identified with the symbol “soul”. As H. Skovoroda emphasizes, the heart in relation to the body is a spiritual substance, the first principle of movement, represented as a soul in a platonic interpretation: “And this ship will lead our ten-headed conversation, as if through ten doors, as Noah's dove, not finding rest anywhere, returned to its heart, to that one which rests in your heart...” (“I tsey korabel povede y nasha desyatyhlava besida, nachebto cherez desyat dvirey, i ya bazhayu, shchob tvoya dusha, yak Noyeva holubytstva, ne znayshovshy nide spokoyu, povernulasya do sertsya svoho, do toho, shcho spochyvaye u sertsii tvoyim ...”) [“Introductory door to Christian benevolence”].

“The Great Explanatory Dictionary of Modern Ukrainian Literary Language” offers the following definition of the token “soul” - “The inner mental world of man // According to religious beliefs –it is the immortal intangible basis in man, which is the essence of his life, is a source of mental phenomena and distinguishes him from animals” [2, p. 333]. According to the “Encyclopedic Dictionary of Symbols of Culture of Ukraine”, the soul is a symbol of immortality, eternity of a believer; Spirit, part of God; life, light; priceless element of three-dimensional structure (body-soul-spirit); a symbol of weightlessness, invisibility, mystery; the spark of the divine Spirit, part of the World Soul, the Monad (in theosophy); a thinking, mobile, harmonious being who can live outside the body; the symbol of the element of the energy information field of the Universe; a symbol of uniqueness and originality; lyricism, aesthetics, emotionality, sensitivity, singing, wit of Ukrainians” [4, p. 245]. The philosopher devoted his most important treatises to the reflections on the “soul caves” of man, that is, self-knowledge and at the same time knowledge of divine wisdom: “The Alphabet of the World”, “Narcissus. Talk about: know yourself”, “Icon of Alcaviad”.

Analyzing Z. Horyk-Berezovska's researches, we state that H. Skovoroda's artistic heritage demonstrates two levels of perception of the world: one level is a disappointment with the world, the other one is a spontaneous belief in the value of the human soul. Interesting from this point of view is H. Skovoroda's Song Twenty-one: “Happiness, but where do you live?” Of all the associations that evoke the concept of “soul”, the most important, as in Plato's view, is the human soul - the mirror of the world. According to this thesis, “a subject and an object have the same nature, the microcosm is equal to the macrocosm” [7, p. 53]. The poet transfers the cosmogonic theme to the psychological plan and therefore he seeks answers to questions, turns to the sky, the moon and the stars, while the soul of his lyrical subject remains a desert. Its interpretation partially reproduces the archetype of the sacred origin, because this image in the poet's lyrics is consistent with the ancient mythological motif. In addition, poetry embodies the ideal of the Baroque, because here appears the artist

- “ascetic philosopher, that is, a man who is close to and understands well the ancient love for all living and earthly things, “but his soul is “filled with thirst for heaven, eternal, imperishable” [9, p. 23].

In H. Skovoroda's creative heritage there are many poems with a dominant “soul”, imbued with a powerful humanistic pathos. This is due to the fact that the poet sought to create a harmonious world out of the chaos of the soul. His lyrics embodies the dialectic of the eidos of the “soul” developed by Plato, and therefore his “soul” is filled with unbearable “boredom”, then flourishes and joy is born in it, it is either “poor” or “enchanted by the sweet voice of ocean sirens” [11, p. 28]. His lyrical hero asks Jesus to appease the perishable passions of the soul: “They torment me, they make my life bitter” [11, p. 37], then he sees “in the soul one word that only it can make happy” [11, p. 35]. This recognizes the dualism of the author's worldview, which is basically harmonious and disharmonious. Thus, the silent and dark cave of the heart contrasts with the light and harmonious life - and this is more than the soul of one individual, it is part of a single soul, a single “great man”.

The existence of the soul of the subject of the work is Jesus in Song Seven:

Crucify my body with yours and nail it to the cross.

Let me not be the whole outside - just be resurrected inside;

Let my appearance dry, if only

Something bloomed inside. Such death is life!

(Rozpny zh iz soboyu y moye Ty tilo i prybyy na khrest,

Nekhay ya ne budu navni tsilyy – aby tilky voskresnuty vsередyni;

Nekhay zovnishnist' moya vysokhne, aby tilky

Shcho inshe vsередyni zatsvilo. Taka smert – zhyt-tya!) [11, p. 22].

This is how the poet presents the original version of the motif of “crucifixion”, popular in ancient Ukrainian literature. Significantly, in the mentioned song the author three times (this number is included in the magic series of numbers: 3, 7, 9, 33) refers to one of the oldest sacred signs - “cross”, where the vertical part of the cross symbolizes the logos, word, divine origin in the man of God - Jesus, and the horizontal part - human nature in him” [5, p. 175]. It is interesting that in H. Skovoroda's poetry this symbolic image is a kind of marker, which means the suffering and crucifixion of the very soul of the lyrical hero (“just to be resurrected inside”).

Experiencing the disharmony of social processes, H. Skovoroda sought peace, internal and external balance, as he wrote in Song Twenty-Four, based on Horace (“Oh, our heavenly peace! Where did you hide from our eyes?”):

We all love you, and you broke us in different ways.

So behind you the sails are crucified on ships,

So that these wings can look for you on other people's sides.

They march after you, destroy cities,
They've been bombing all their lives, but when
will they get it?

(My zh tebe usi lyubymo, a ty rozbyv nas po
riznykh shlyakhakh.

To zh za tobouy vitryla rozpynayut' na kora-
blyakh,

Shchob tebe si kryla mohly rozshukaty po chu-
zhykh storonakh.

Za tobouy marshyruyut', ruynuyut' mista,

Tsilyy vik bombarduyut', ale chy distanut' koly?)
[11, p. 34].

It should be noted that the image of the "heart"
testified to a wide range of emotional experiences from
joy to sorrow. In particular, the work "Garden...",
according to the Slovak researcher Z. Henyk-
Berezovska, is permeated by the leading H.
Skovoroda's antithesis: "against sadness he puts
forward peace of mind, happiness, against expressive
overplanting - a sense of spleen" [3, p. 47]. For
example, in Song Nineteen, the poet admits:

You will kill the beast of evil when you take a
sharp knife,

And you will not overcome boredom, although
you will have a good sword

(Zviryaku zlu zakolesh, koly viz'mesh hostryy
nizh,

A skuky ne podoliyesh, khoch i matymesh dobryy
mech) [11, p. 30].

Obviously, the reproduction of binary oppositions
of the world order is an immanent feature of H.
Skovoroda's poetics, as P. Belous also claims in his
research (heaven - hell, darkness - light, fire - stone,
earth - sky, body - soul, spring - winter, paradise -
garden - city, etc.) [1, p. 39]. With his reader, the
philosopher shares the secret: "Your happiness is inside
you, here its center is buried: knowing yourself, you
know everything, not knowing yourself, in the dark you
will walk and be afraid of fear, where it will not be" [6,
p. 120].

An important idea of indestructibility or "re-exist-
ence" of the soul the poet finds in the surrounding
objects as a non-living substance - and the mysterious
eye again is an allusion to the container of the soul:

The Spirit is the abyss in man, the abyss wider than
all waters and heavens;

You will never saturate that abyss only with what
enchants the eye

(Dukh - se bezodnya v lyudyni, bezodnya shyrsha
usikh vod i nebes;

Voviky ne nasytysh toyi bezodni tilky tym, shcho
charuye oko) [11, p. 25],

that sees that matter has a spiritual connection with
the being; a mysterious voice that indicates the essence
of this connection. On this basis, H. Skovoroda
introduces into his works images of physical nature,
animates it, giving it a rational and concrete-sensory
justification:

There is a sycamore tree above the mountain,

That nods its head to everyone nods,

Strong winds blow,

The sycamore branches are broken;

And the willow trees make a low noise

And they drag me to sleep

(Stoyit yavir nad horoyu,

Vse kyvaye holovoyu,

Buyni vitry povivayut,

Vity yavoru lamayut;

A verbochky shumlyat nyzko

I tyahnut mene do sna) [11, p. 30].

H. Skovoroda went on to rethink the poetic image
of the willow, endowed by Christianity with a negative-
sad connotation, interpreting this reality in Song Three
("Dear spring, ah, has come! Winter is fierce, ah,
passed!") as following:

My soul is a willow, and you are water;

Feed me in this water. Comfort me in this
trouble...

(Dusha moya verba, a ty - voda;

Hoduy mene v siy vodi. Utish mene v siy bidi...)

[11, p. 19].

Willow, symbolizing loneliness and sadness,
combined with water is a symbol of love, health and
longevity. Minor and major feelings of the work are due
to specific factors, conscious states of nature and the
poet's soul, which corresponded to the ideal of
ecoharmony (perfection of the beauty of nature and the
human soul commensurate with it).

Therefore, between the "soul" and "nature",
"soul" and "things" the relation of identity is
established. The ideological content of the third song is
closely connected with Slavic mythology. Thus, the
songs of the Slavic peoples represent many stories of
transformation. In particular, our ancestors sincerely
believed that after the loss of the human body, the soul
takes the form of a tree or a bird and for some time
continues to live in the afterlife:

Oh, my God - you are my hail!

Oh my God, you are my garden,

Innocence - these are my flowers, love and peace

-

here are my fruits

(O, Bozhe miy - ty miy hrad!

O, Bozhe miy - ty miy sad,

Nevynnist - oto moyi kvitky, lyubov i spokiy -

oto moyi plody) [11, p. 19].

The image of the plant, captured by him in motion,
on a metaphorical level represents the essential aspects
of the topos "garden" (universal image, immanent to
the traditions of Baroque literature): garden - the world,
garden - the human soul, garden - wisdom and
knowledge. Thus, Song Twenty-eight "Come up to
heaven - at least the Garden of Versailles" is about the
garden as a creative ideal to which a person must strive,
because for balance, peace of mind a man must know
Skovoroda's "visible and invisible in things".

In H. Skovoroda's work, this symbol "garden" is
pervasive, as evidenced by the title of the poetic book
"Garden of Divine Songs". Embodying the motif of the
garden, the author accordingly structured a collection
of poetry, selecting from his records 30 texts (symbol-
ism of the magic number), the sacred nature is deter-
mined by the fundamental concept of the creative role
of the Word embodied in Scripture" (I. Isichenko). Ac-
cording to the researcher L. Sazonova, in this collection

“naturally appears long-known in the literature symbolic assimilation of the soul of the garden, flowers and fruits - spiritual values” [10, p. 182]. We find a deepening of this idea in the work of the renowned researcher of Ukrainian Baroque V. Shevchuk: “topos “garden” is used as a concept of enlightened soul, flowers and fruits - spiritual values and as a garden of sciences (Song Twenty-Seven “You make the garden, drink this holy garden”) [12, p. 205], in which the poet associates the Kharkiv Collegium with the “Garden of Higher Sciences”, and likens the activities of the Bishop of Belgorod Joasaph Mitkevych to the work of a gardener:

Do not allow heresies poison
And drive away all the dishonest,
Let him give birth to spiritual kings,
The kingdom of the king, embracing all...
(Ne dopusty yeresey yad
I vidzheny vsikh bezchesnykh,
Rodyt nekhay dukhovnykh tsariv,
Tsarstvo tsarya, obnyavshy usikh...)

Thus, the soul, according to H. Skovoroda is the core value of man, his life. In order to know himself, man, created in the image of God, must care for the purity of his own soul, and only then the truth of the world will be revealed to him.

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